

A Descriptive Study to Assess the Effect of Process Addiction on Global Functioning Status Among Older People in Selected Area Pathalgaon, Jashpur District, Chhattisgarh

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Abstract: **Background:** Process addiction refers to compulsive behaviors that an individual engages in and continues to do despite harmful consequences. An older people are defined by the United Nations as person who is over 60 years of age. However, families and communities often use other socio-cultural referents to define age, including family status (grandparents), physical appearance or age-related health conditions. **Aim:** The present study is aimed to assess the effect of process addiction on global functioning status among older peoples. **Setting and Design:** A quantitative research approach with non-experimental research design was adopted for the study. The study focused on older peoples from selected area Pathalgaon, Jashpur (C.G.) **Material and Methods:** Totally 60 older peoples above 65 years of age from the selected area Pathalgaon, jashpur (C.G.) after obtaining informed consent. Data was collected using 48 questionnaires covering the area i.e., Self-Structured Questionnaire (3-point rating scale) to assess extent of process addiction among older people and Self-Structured Questionnaire (3-point rating scale) to evaluate global functioning status among older people. **Results:** As the present study aimed to find out the effect of process addiction on global functioning status among older people was statistically analyzed using student's 't' test. As t_{cal} were 5.63 which is more than t_{tab} at 0.05% level of significance. There is significant association between process addiction and Education qualification ($\chi^2_{cal} 14.16 > \chi^2_{tab} 12.59$). There is significant association between global functioning status and marital status ($\chi^2_{cal} 17.7 > \chi^2_{tab} 12.59$).

Keywords: effect of process addiction, global functioning status, older people.

1. Introduction

Addiction is a compulsive need for and use of a habit-forming substance. It is accepted as a mental illness in the diagnostic nomenclature and results in substantial health, social and economic problems. National survey on drug use and health (NSDUH2004) found that of individual aged 50 or older, 12.2% were heavy drinkers, 3.2% were binge drinkers and 1.8% used illicit drugs. The section title also can be copied and paste it, when you need new section and type the section heading as per your requirement.

2. Objectives

- 1) To assess the extent of process addiction among older people.
- 2) To evaluate global functioning status among older people.
- 3) To find out the effect of process addiction on global functioning status among older people.
- 4) To find out the association between process addiction and selected socio-demographic variables among older people.
- 5) To find out the association between global functioning status and selected socio-demographic variables among older people.

3. Material and Methods

A descriptive study was conducted using non-experimental research design. Sample in the study were older peoples fulfilling the inclusion criteria at the selected settings. older peoples have diagnosed preexisting psychological, social and occupational problems, have sensory deficits, have diagnosed addiction other than TV. series were excluded. Self-Structured Questionnaire (3-point rating scale) to assess extent of process addiction among older people and Self-Structured Questionnaire (3-point rating scale) to evaluate global functioning status among older people.

A representative sample was selected using purposive sampling from the population of older peoples in selected area Pathalgaon, Jashpur (C.G.).

Frequency and percentage analysis was done to describe the demographic characteristics of the older peoples. The chi-square analysis used to determine the association between socio-demographic variable and process addiction. 't' test analysis to find out the effect of process addiction on global functioning status.

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4. Results and Discussion

A. Distribution of subjects According to Socio-Demographic Variables

In present study, socio demographic data elicit that among the study sample, maximum older people 34(56.6%) belongs to 65-69 year of age and 31(51.66%) were females. 47(78.33%) were educated up to primary school while 11(18.33%) educated upto high school. majority of study sample 33(55%) dependent on family while majority of study sample was getting sufficient perceived support from family that is 58 (96.66%). 4(6.66%) of study samples are separated from spouse half of the study samples 45(75%) were living with Their family members.

B. Extent of Process Addiction

1) Area wise analysis of extent of process addiction among older peoples

Process addiction on T.V. series among older people in terms of its domains. With regard to extent of desire on watching mean percentage score obtained was 73.2 % (5.13±1.29) and their dependency on it was also found to as mean percentage score obtained was 60.4% (6.65±1.68). With regard to loss of control mean percentage score was 60.8%(6.08±1.69), whereas intensity of getting over engaged was found to minimum as mean percentage is 52.5% (6.31±1.69) respectively.

2) Overall analysis of extent of process addiction among older peoples

Majority of older people i.e., 42 (70%) had moderate addiction which ranges from 17-25 score, 15 (25%) had severe addiction which ranges from >26, where's only 3 (5%) had mild addiction which ranges from <16 score.

C. Global functioning status among older peoples

1) Area wise analysis of global functioning status among older peoples

Global functioning status among older people is measured with regard to assessment of psychological function, assessment of social function, assessment of ADL function. Assessment of psychological function mean percentage score obtained was 65% (7.8 ±1.47) assessment of social function mean percentage score obtained was 63.27 % (6.9±2.67) and assessment of ADL function mean percentage score was 67.2 % (6.05±1.28).

2) Overall analysis of extent of process addiction among older peoples

Global functioning status categorised in various levels based on the range of score as low active, moderate active and severe active. Majority of the older people i.e., 54 (90%) had better function in global functioning status and 6 (10%) had good function in global functioning status.

Above finding is supported by Meera L (2022) [48], Pune Maharashtra, India where internet addiction of adolescents is evaluated. Findings depicts prevalence of global functioning were 24.1% were found to be prone to active and 3.1% were probably active severely as per the scale range of global function.

D. Analysis to find out the effect of process addiction on global functioning status among older people

The mean in process addiction is 21.7, mean score percentage is 60.2, SD is 4.83, whereas the mean in global functioning status is 7.83, mean score percentage is 65, SD is 3.59.

Therefore H1 i.e. highly significant effect of process addiction on global functioning status among older people as calculated' value= 5.63 which is more than value of 't'= 0.05% level of significance.

There is significant association between process addiction and education as chi square value calculated (14.16) is greater than the table value (12.59) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, H2 i.e., there is significant association between process addiction with selected socio demographic variables among older people is ACCEPTED in regards to education qualification.

Above finding is supported by the study of American journal of medicine (2018) each of the four scales was significantly correlated with patients global perceptions of their quality of life (p<0.001). The ability of the health –status scales to discriminate between patients with differing global quality of life was generally good, especially for the physical capacity (c statistic=0.72) and psychological distress scales (c statistics =0.70).

E. Association between global functioning stats and selected socio-demographic variables

There was significant association of the study variable global functioning status with marital status as chi square value calculated (17.7) was greater than (12.59) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, H3 i.e., there is association between global functioning status with selected socio demographic variables is ACCEPTED in regards to marital status. (Married and staying with their spouse are proved to have better global functioning.

5. Implication

A. In Nursing Education

In nursing curriculum, care of old age shall be given more importance including interventions for the current problems like loneliness and isolation among late adulthood.

Nurse educator should take responsibility about updating of current scenario about effect of process addiction and global functioning status among older people.

B. In Nursing Practice

Community health nurses shall arrange provision in old age home and elders in home care to be achieve in their areas of internet other than series like cooking, reading, knitting etc.

Clinical nurse can use the findings of the study to assess the level of global functioning status.

C. In Nursing Research

Nurse researcher can utilize this study in developing nursing theory/conceptual framework.

Conduct more nursing research with the aim to understand the role of process addiction and its effect among older people.

The nurse use research findings in practice research design

to generate knowledge to guide older people to avoid regular use of television and internet media.

6. Recommendation

A study can be conducted to assess process addiction in older people.

A similar study can be undertaken with the large sample for wider generalization of the present study. The same study can be replicated in other setting.

7. Conclusion

Results obtained in the study that majority of older people i.e. 3 (70%) had moderate addiction which ranges from 17 -25 score, 15(25%) had severe addiction which ranges from >26, where's only 3 (5%) had mild addiction which ranges from <16 score. t-test was calculated and t was found to be +5.63. Therefore H1 i.e. highly significant effect of process addiction on global functioning status among older people as calculated' value= 5.63 which is more than value of 't'= 0.05%level of significance.

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